

Stavanger, Norway

EUROCORR 2025

7 - 11 September

8 - 11 September 2025 - Stavanger/N

Book of Lecture Abstracts

(as of 19 August 2025)

EFC Event Number 520

Initial stages of corrosion degradation of chitosan-based coatings on Mg alloys probed by dynamic electrochemical impedance spectroscopy

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The development of reliable metallic implant materials designed to replace bone tissue and fix bone fractures gained immense scientific and practical interest. Such materials should combine biological compatibility with human organisms and mechanical properties similar to those of native bone tissue. The development and implementation of biodegradable implants is a promising way to eliminate the problem of repeated surgical interventions. For this, Mg alloys are extensively examined. At the same time, to provide reliable antibacterial and corrosion protection at the first stages of the use, polymer coatings are deposited onto Mg alloys. Recently, we have shown that the implementation of multisine dynamic electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (DEIS) is a useful tool to eliminate the problem of system non-stationarity in the corrosion measurements of Mg alloys. Moreover, DEIS is also useful for examining the degradation of the polymer coatings in the initial stages of corrosion. The aim of the present study was to examine the initial stages of degradation of chitosan-based coatings on Mg alloys in Hank's solution utilizing the DEIS technique.

Different coatings based on low, medium, and high molecular weight chitosan were deposited on the surface of AZ31 and WE43 alloys by electrophoretic deposition from aqueous mixtures with ethanol with and without coordination ions. Their properties were characterized by a set of physicochemical methods. Reference samples without coatings were also examined. Corrosion experiments by DEIS confirmed the usefulness of this technique to precise characterization of the degradation profiles of polymer coatings in initial stages of *in vitro* corrosion experiments.

Funding

This work was financially supported by the National Science Centre of Poland under the Sonatina 5 grant [grant number: 2021/40/C/ST5/00266].